

Kinetics and Mechanism of Oxidation of Benzal Methylphenyl Sulphides by Vanadium(v)

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The rates of oxidation of benzal methylphenyl sulphide (BMS) and some substituted BMS's by vanadium(v) ion were measured in aqueous acetic acid in the presence of perchloric acid. The reaction is first order in [V^V] and fraction in [BMS]. The reaction is acid-catalysed. Addition of NaClO₄ had no effect on the rate. The rates were also found to be sensitive to solvent polarity. Formation of an intermediate complex between V^V and BMS and subsequent decomposition of this in a slow step, involving the attack of oxidant on the non-bonded electrons of sulphide sulphur is proposed as the probable mechanism.

Benzal methylphenyl sulphide, Ph-CH=CH-S-Ph, has two reaction sites, viz. carbon-carbon double bond and the sulphide sulphur. In order to ascertain the actual site of attack in the oxidation of BMS, kinetics of oxidation of BMS by V^V having substituents in both the phenyl rings has been studied. Though Kohler and Potter¹ reported the oxidation of benzal methyltolyl sulphide by hydrogen peroxide in aqueous acetic acid and the product was identified as the respective sulphoxide, no attempts have so far been made to study the kinetics of oxidation of these substrates. Vanadium(v) which has been used for the oxidation of a number of organic compounds, is not used for the oxidation of BMS and hence the title investigation.

Results and Discussion

The reactions are first order with respect to V^V. Further, the values of k_{obs} are independent of the initial concentration of V^V. The reaction rate increases with an increase in the concentration of the sulphide but not linearly (Table 1). A plot (not shown) of $1/k_{obs}$ against $1/[sulphide]$ is linear ($r = 0.999$) with an intercept on the rate coordinate. Thus a reaction pathway involving formation of a complex in a fast pre-equilibrium and its slow decomposition is contemplated. Reactions involving Michaelis-Menten type kinetics have been already reported in the oxidation of sulphides² and also in the oxidation by V^V.^{3,4} The rates of oxidation of sulphides increase with increase in the concentration of perchloric acid. The plot of $\log k_{obs}$ versus $\log [H^+]$ is linear (not shown) with a slope of 1.1 indicating that the order with respect to $[H^+]$ is one. The hydrogen ion dependence of the form, $k_{obs} = a + b [H^+]$ indicates that there is a likely basic site on one of the reactants for protonation, and the greater reactivity of the protonated species compared to the unprotonated form can usually be rationalised. The terms a and b can be attributed to reaction of unprotonated and protonated forms of the vanadium(v) species arising from the protic equilibrium,

TABLE 1—RATE CONSTANTS FOR THE OXIDATION OF BMS BY V^V AT 308 K IN 70% (V/V) AQUEOUS ACETIC ACID

10 ³ [V ^V] <i>M</i>	10 ² [BMS] <i>M</i>	10 [HClO ₄] <i>M</i>	10 ⁴ k_{obs} s ⁻¹
1.0	2.0	4.0	4.89
1.5	2.0	4.0	4.65
2.0	2.0	4.0	4.62
2.5	2.0	4.0	4.59
3.0	2.0	4.0	4.37
2.0	1.0	4.0	2.21
2.0	3.0	4.0	6.49
2.0	4.0	4.0	7.97
2.0	6.0	4.0	9.84
2.0	8.0	4.0	11.32
2.0	2.0	2.0	2.16
2.0	2.0	3.0	3.48
2.0	2.0	5.0	5.81
2.0	2.0	6.0	7.22
2.0	2.0 ^a	4.0	4.71
2.0	2.0 ^b	4.0	4.64
2.0	2.0 ^c	4.0	2.89
2.0	2.0 ^d	4.0	1.38

*Contained ^a0.01 M and ^b0.02 M sodium perchlorate; ^c0.01 M and ^d0.02 M acrylonitrile

Both species contribute to the reaction but the protonated species has the greater reactivity. Thus, under the experimental conditions, it is assumed that the V^V exists as V(OH)₃²⁺, which is the reactive oxidising species^{3,6}. The increase in oxidising power of V^V with increase in $[H^+]$ is mainly due to the increase in the oxidation potential of V^V species. Further, it is supported by the sluggish nature of the reaction in the absence of added acid.

Addition of sodium perchlorate did not affect the rate while acrylonitrile which is capable of trapping the free radicals retards the rate appreciably (Table 1).

Solvent effect : The oxidation of BMS was studied in

solvents containing different proportions of acetic acid and water. The rate of oxidation increases as the amount of acetic acid in the solvent is increased (Table 2). The observed solvent effect (Table 2) leads to the reported conclusion⁷, to which a decrease in dielectric constant should increase the reaction rate for the reaction of a positive ion and dipolar molecule. In fact, the same was observed in the present reaction, when $\log k_{178}$ versus the inverse of the permittivity of the solvent yielded a straight-line with a positive slope. This coupled with the effect of $[H^+]$ on the rates, leads to the conclusion that $V(OH)_3^{2+}$ is the reactive species of V^V .

TABLE 2—EFFECT OF SOLVENT COMPOSITION ON THE OXIDATION RATE

AcOH %(v/v)	D	$10^4 k_{obs}$ s ⁻¹	$10^3 k_{178}$ dm ^{0.78} mol ^{-0.78} s ⁻¹
50	43.10	1.81	3.83
60	35.72	2.77	5.86
70	28.34	4.62	9.77
80	20.96	10.67	22.56
90	13.58	32.31	68.31

Substituent effects : The rates of oxidation of a number of *para*-substituents in both the phenyl rings (phenyl moiety of phenyl acetylene and phenyl moiety of thiophenol) of BMS were determined at different temperatures. The equilibrium constant (K_2) was evaluated from the double-reciprocal plots and for the parent it was found to be 5.70. The values of K_2 for *p*-CH₃ present in thiophenol and phenylacetylene moiety are 5.65 and 5.68 respectively, and that for *p*-Cl 5.72 and 5.67 respectively. It indicates that the formation constant (K_2) of the V^V -substrate complex is not sensitive to the nature of the substituent. However, the decomposition of the complex is sensitive to the nature of the substituents. The calculated rate constants and the activation parameters for the oxidation of various substituted benzal methylphenyl sulphides are given in Table 3. A linear correlation ($r = 0.992$) between $\log k_{178}$ values at 293 and 318 K for eleven sulphides indicates that all the benzal methylphenyl sulphides are oxidised by the same mechanism⁵. The value of the isokinetic temperature is 361.6 K.

Correlation analysis and reactivity : Data in Table 3 show that the effects of *para*-substituents in phenylacetylene ring of BMS was smaller compared to the effect of same substituents present in thiophenol ring of BMS. Rates of oxidation of *para*-substituted BMS in each ring correlate well with Hammett substituent constants yielding negative reaction constants (Table 4). The negative ρ values indicate that a positively charged reaction centre is developed during the course of reaction. The value obtained is in agreement with that observed for other free radical processes^{8,9} (whose ρ value normally lies between -0.5 and -1.5). The large negative ΔS^\ddagger value is suggestive of a more rigid active complex.

TABLE 3—CALCULATED RATE CONSTANTS AND ACTIVATION PARAMETERS FOR THE OXIDATION OF *para*-SUBSTITUTED BMS BY V^V *

[BMS] = 2.0×10^{-2} M, $[V^V] = 2.0 \times 10^{-3}$ [HClO₄] = 0.4 M,
Solvent 70% (v/v) aqueous AcOH

Substituent	$10^3 k_{178}$ dm ^{0.78} mol ^{-0.78} s ⁻¹				ΔH^\ddagger kJ mol ⁻¹	$-\Delta S^\ddagger$ JK ⁻¹ mol ⁻¹
	293K	303K	308K	318K		
H	2.87	6.14	9.77	18.93	56.48	100.83
<i>p</i> -OCH ₃	9.48	15.82	22.65	40.68	42.95	137.38
<i>p</i> -CH ₃	7.96	13.62	16.94	32.45	40.56	146.95
<i>p</i> -F	2.49	5.88	8.73	17.37	57.78	97.38
<i>p</i> -Cl	1.50	3.42	5.67	11.46	61.12	90.38
<i>p</i> -Br	1.32	3.18	5.07	10.98	63.41	83.61
<i>p</i> -NO ₂	0.37	1.02	1.73	4.45	74.41	55.62
<i>p</i> -OCH ₃ ^a	8.31	13.04	17.57	31.68	39.02	151.96
<i>p</i> -CH ₃ ^a	7.79	11.74	15.69	29.05	38.28	155.17
<i>p</i> -Cl ^a	2.29	5.89	8.03	17.52	60.02	90.36
<i>p</i> -NO ₂ ^a	0.71	2.08	3.34	8.02	72.62	57.13

^aSubstituents in phenylacetylene moiety

TABLE 4—TEMPERATURE DEPENDENCE OF THE REACTION CONSTANTS

Temp K	ρ	r
<i>para</i> -Substituents in thiophenol moiety		
293	-1.37	0.980
303	-1.16	0.987
308	-1.06	0.993
318	-0.92	0.989
<i>para</i> -Substituents in phenylacetylene moiety		
293	-1.02	0.975
303	-0.74	0.981
308	-0.68	0.993
318	-0.56	0.988

Mechanism and rate law : Formation of products C₆H₅CH₂CHO and C₆H₅SSC₆H₅ can be explained only on the basis of attack at sulphur and not at $-C=C-$. Therefore, it is reasonable to assume that V^V coordinates with non-bonded electrons of sulphide sulphur forming an intermediate complex, which breaks down in a slow step to give steryl cation and free radical C₆H₅S. The presence of free radical was confirmed by positive polymerisation of acrylonitrile added to the reaction mixture. Further, oxidation of phenylacetaldehyde is ruled out since the reactions were conducted under the conditions of [oxidant] \ll [BMS]. From the foregoing discussion, the mechanism of oxidation of BMS by V^V ion can be depicted as follows (assuming the predominant reaction path of the protonated vanadium(v) species) :

The scheme leads to the rate law,

$$\text{Rate} = \frac{k K_1 K_2 [\text{BMS}] [\text{VO}_2^+] [\text{H}_3\text{O}^+]}{1 + K_2 [\text{BMS}]}$$

$$k_{\text{obs}} = \frac{k K_1 K_2 [\text{BMS}] [\text{H}_3\text{O}^+]}{1 + K_2 [\text{BMS}]}$$

where, k_{obs} is the observed pseudo-first order rate constant. The above equation may be rewritten as

$$\frac{1}{k_{\text{obs}}} = \frac{1}{k K_1 K_2 [\text{BMS}] [\text{H}_3\text{O}^+]} + \frac{1}{k K_1 [\text{H}_3\text{O}^+]}$$

At constant $[\text{H}_3\text{O}^+]$, a plot of $1/k_{\text{obs}}$ versus $1/[\text{BMS}]$ should give a straight-line with an intercept. In fact, the same was observed in the present investigations, supporting the proposed mechanism.

Experimental

Benzal methylphenyl sulphides were prepared¹ and purified by distillation under reduced pressure. Acetic acid was refluxed over chromic oxide and acetic anhydride for 3 h and then fractionated. All other reagents, were of analytical grade.

Kinetic measurements : Reactions were carried out under pseudo-first order conditions by keeping an excess

($\times 10$ or greater) of the sulphide over vanadium(v). The solvent was 3 : 1 (v/v) acetic acid-water unless otherwise stated. The reactions were followed upto 80% reaction by adding definite amount of vanadium(v) solution to a known excess of ferrous sulphate solution and back-titrating the unreacted ferrous sulphate against standard vanadium(v) solution using barium diphenylaminosulphonate indicator. The pseudo-first order rate constant (k_{obs}) was computed from the linear least-squares plot of $\log [\text{V}^{\text{V}}]$ versus time. Duplicate runs showed the rate constants to be reproducible to within $\pm 3\%$.

Product analysis : In a typical experiment, benzal methylphenyl sulphide (4.24 g, 20 mmol) was added to aqueous acetic acid (100 ml) containing perchloric acid (0.5 M) and ammonium metavanadate (1.17 g, 10 mmol). The mixture was allowed to stand for 36 h, then neutralised and the resulting white solid was dried (0.77 g, 83%) which was found identical (m.p. and FT-ir) with diphenyl disulphide. The filtrate of the neutralised reaction mixture was treated with an excess (150 ml) of a saturated solution of 2,4-dinitrophenylhydrazine in 2 M HCl and kept overnight in a refrigerator. The precipitated 2,4-dinitrophenylhydrazone (DNP) was filtered off, dried, crystallised from ethanol. The yields of DNP before and after recrystallisation were 2.64 (88%) and 2.21 g (74%) respectively. The DNP was found identical (m.p. and mixed m.p.) with the DNP of phenyl acetaldehyde.

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